

STUDIES IN MEDIA,
INNOVATION & TECHNOLOGY
RESEARCH GROUP

MARIA
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The European Institute
for Innovation through
Health Data

WORKSHOP

How to Put Data Quality on the Agenda of
Your Organization's Management?

OHDSI BELGIUM

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Report

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Introduction

The workshop "How to put Data Quality on the agenda of your organization's management?" was organized by OHDSI Belgium to explore strategies for enhancing and harmonizing data quality pipelines across financial and clinical applications. The event aimed to equip data scientists with practical skills to raise awareness about the importance of data quality and to provide managers with tools to align and implement effective quality practices throughout their organizations.

The workshop gathered 32 participants from diverse backgrounds, including clinical data scientists, healthcare managers, and industry professionals, ensuring a rich exchange of knowledge and expertise.

We are particularly grateful for the leadership and expertise of Nicky Van der Vekens (VZW Maria Middelaes), Noëlla Pierlet (ZOL), Jens Declerck (i~HD), and Melissa Wittens (imec-SMIT-VUB). Their guidance was instrumental in shaping the event's structure and delivering meaningful, impactful content. This report captures the key insights and takeaways from the workshop to serve as a resource for future initiatives.

32 health data enthusiasts participated in this workshop - #DataSavesLives

Key insights & takeaways

Data Quality concepts

- Data quality is **context-dependent** and must align with the specific needs of the end-user. Dimensions like accuracy, completeness, and timeliness vary in importance depending on whether the focus is patient-level data (clinicians) or population-level data (researchers).
- Challenges include creating frameworks that remain applicable across different contexts and stages of the **data lifecycle**. Practical frameworks must balance continuous quality improvement with seamless data flow.

Data Quality dimensions

- **Accuracy:** Data must align with true values.
- **Completeness:** All necessary data elements must be present.
- **Timeliness:** Data should be available when needed.
- **Reliability:** Data must remain consistent across contexts and use cases.

To address these dimensions, organizations must implement tailored strategies for improvement, such as structured lifecycle management, effective governance, and transparent processes.

Data Flow optimization

- Manual workflows often lead to inefficiencies and errors. Streamlining processes through automation and validation mechanisms can significantly improve data quality while saving time and reducing administrative burdens.
- Transparent trajectory analysis enables organizations to identify bottlenecks, co-create solutions with stakeholders, and enhance overall system efficiency.

Clinical Decision Support Systems (CDSS)

- CDSS should deliver actionable insights at the right time and in the right format.
- Effective CDSS design prioritizes:
 - User-centered interfaces that are intuitive and minimalistic.
 - Real-time actionable data tailored to clinician workflows.
- Dashboards must answer critical clinical questions rather than simply present data, enhancing decision-making and patient outcomes.

European Projects driving Data Quality innovation

- **QUANTUM project:** Aiming to develop a data quality label for the European Health Data Space, enabling the identification of high-quality datasets for secondary use.
- **IDERHA project:** Leveraging AI to integrate and analyze health data, improving outcomes like early cancer detection and ensuring compliance with evolving regulations.

Roles & Responsibilities

- Data quality improvement requires a shared responsibility among stakeholders, including management, care providers, and technical teams.
- Engaging stakeholders early and co-creating solutions are essential for sustained improvement.
- A dedicated data team is crucial to support care providers and ensure practical implementation.

Change Management for Data Quality

- Data quality improvement is an ongoing process that requires transparency, education, and alignment of goals across stakeholders.
- The ROI for healthcare providers lies in efficiency gains, reduced administrative burdens, and smoother workflows, which are achievable through co-creation and automation.

Use-Case presentation - Data flow optimization

Practical steps to cut costs and enhance efficiency

The workshop started with a presentation by [Nicky Van der Vekens](#), Digital Hospital Coordinator at VZW Maria Middelaers, showcasing a real-life example of their hospital reimbursement workflow. It provided participants with practical insights into identifying inefficiencies, improving data quality, and reducing administrative burdens.

The [presentation](#) was structured into five phases, each providing a step-by-step framework for understanding and addressing data quality challenges.

Phase 1: Identifying the problem

The presentation began by introducing a relatable problem scenario based on the reimbursement of hospital procedures through RIZIV/INAMI. The specific challenge revolved around:

- The registration of hospital procedures for invoicing purposes.
- The complexity of using nomenclature numbers for procedures, particularly for anesthetic procedures, where the nomenclature may not align with the type of surgery performed.
- The manual nature of these processes, often handled by physicians or administrative staff, introduced opportunities for errors.

This phase provided participants with a clear and tangible example of how small issues in data registration could lead to broader inefficiencies.

Phase 2: Contextual overview of the data flow

In Phase 2, a detailed overview of the patient data flow was presented, illustrating how information moves through the hospital system:

- Registration at the hospital kiosk or reception.
- Documentation by administrative staff at the secretary's office.
- Data creation and consultation during the surgeon's appointment (e.g., medical history, medications, type of surgery, surgeon's details).
- Completion of pre-admission questionnaires (physical and digital), with validation steps.
- Transfer of the patient to the operating room, followed by the surgery.
- Documentation by the anesthesiologist during surgery, including the name and code of administered drugs, timestamps, and surgery type.
- Transfer of data to the office manager for manual entry into the XDE Tarfac system, with final checks by the financial department before issuing the invoice.

This phase demonstrated the complexity of data flows in healthcare settings, highlighting the risks associated with manual data handling and fragmented processes.

Contextual overview of the data flow

Use-Case presentation - Data flow optimization

Practical steps to cut costs and enhance efficiency

Phase 3: Problem analysis

In this phase, Nicky and her team focused on identifying areas for improvement in the data flow. A set of key questions guided the analysis:

1. What could go wrong?

- Identified vulnerabilities, such as errors in manual data entry by anesthesiologists or office managers.
- Risks of misplacing or losing paper documents during the workflow.

2. What is the effect on data quality?

- Potential for incomplete, inaccurate, or inconsistent data entries.
- Reduced reliability of datasets for downstream processes.

3. What are the direct/indirect consequences of these errors?

- Delays in reimbursement due to inaccurate data submission.
- Increased administrative workload to track and correct errors.

4. Are there financial consequences?

- Errors in invoicing could result in revenue losses or delayed payments for the hospital.

By addressing these questions, the team could systematically identify and prioritize problem areas. This structured approach laid the groundwork for Phase 4.

Identifying areas of improvement

Phase 4: Iterative problem-solving

Building on the insights from Phase 3, the team implemented an iterative problem-solving process aimed at addressing the vulnerabilities in the data flow. This phase included testing and refining solutions to ensure practical and impactful improvements in data quality and workflow efficiency.

Use-Case presentation - Data flow optimization

Practical steps to cut costs and enhance efficiency

Phase 4: Iterative problem-solving

The key steps included:

1. Reducing manual steps:

- Transitioning from paper documentation to digital tools for anesthesiologists, allowing real-time logging of essential details such as drug names, codes, timestamps, and surgery types.
- Automating the transfer of data from clinical records to the XDE Tarfac system to minimize manual input errors and ensure consistency.

2. Implementing validation alerts:

- Introducing automated alerts to flag missing or inconsistent data at critical points in the workflow, preventing errors from propagating further.
- These alerts enabled faster issue resolution, reducing administrative overhead and ensuring smoother downstream processes.

3. Dashboard and visualization tool:

- A key outcome of the iterative process was the development of a dashboard/visualization tool designed to provide real-time insights into the workflow.
- The dashboard displayed validation alerts in an intuitive format, helping staff quickly identify and address bottlenecks or data inconsistencies.
- This visualization tool was integrated into the existing system to enhance visibility, promote accountability, and ensure that corrective actions could be taken efficiently.

The iterative nature of this process allowed for continuous feedback and refinement, ensuring that each solution was not only effective but also well-adapted to the hospital's operational realities.

Phase 5: Evaluating the impact

After implementing the iterative problem-solving steps, the process improvements yielded measurable results. The evaluation of the changes implemented in the **RPA Anesthesia workflow for 2021** highlighted several key outcomes:

- **Time savings:** The automation of the workflow resulted in a **time gain of 577 hours**. Of the 25.000 cases processed, only about 2.000 (~8%) still required manual interaction, significantly reducing the manual workload.
- **Improved Data Completeness:** The introduction of validation alerts and the shift from paper to digital documentation eliminated missing values caused by misplaced paper records. Arrival data was also fully captured, thanks to real-time notifications.
- **Efficiency gains:** Automating previously manual steps allowed the hospital to save **0,5 Full-Time Equivalent (FTE)**, reallocating resources to other areas of need.
- **Enhanced Data Quality:** With fewer manual interventions and improved transparency, the hospital saw a steady improvement in the overall quality and reliability of its data.

Use-Case presentation - Data flow optimization

What's next? Scaling the lessons learned

With the demonstrated success of the RPA Anesthesia process, the hospital team has set its sights on leveraging these lessons in other areas of operation. Potential applications include:

1. Expanding automation:

- Implementing RPA without the need for "visual control" by the office manager, enables further reduction in manual oversight.
- Eliminating manual exports to streamline data transfers.

2. Introducing new procedures:

- Extending the optimized processes to include additional procedures such as epidural anesthesia.

3. Scaling to new sites and departments:

- Rolling out the improved workflows in new hospital sites and specialized departments like the Pain Centre and Intensive Care Unit.

These steps aim to further solidify the hospital's commitment to efficiency and data-driven decision-making while continuing to demonstrate the benefits of change management.

The role of change management in data quality

The success of this use case reinforced an important message: **change management is fundamentally about education and transparency**. The hospital team emphasized the need for a **step-by-step approach** to implementing changes, ensuring each adjustment is visible and its impact is clearly communicated. This transparency not only builds trust but also helps staff anticipate the benefits of each change.

To ensure that these small, incremental changes were visible and actionable, the team relied on the dashboard and alerting tools. The intuitive user interface made these tools accessible to all stakeholders, further driving adoption and engagement.

A critical incentive for healthcare professionals and medical doctors to participate in the change management process was the demonstration of the **direct financial impact of missing data**. By showing how data gaps led to measurable financial losses, the team was able to secure buy-in and promote a culture of accountability and continuous improvement.

This use case illustrated how education, transparency, and alignment of goals can drive successful transformation, serving as a model for other organizations to emulate as they embark on their own data quality improvement journeys.

Clinical Decision Support Systems - Enhancing safety and efficacy through design and implementation

Introduction to Clinical Decision Support Systems (CDSS)

The second part of the workshop focused on the design, functionality, and impact of Clinical Decision Support Systems (CDSS). Led by Melissa Wittens (senior researcher at imec-SMIT-VUB), this session delved into how CDSS can be optimized to improve safety, efficacy, and user experience in healthcare settings. The [presentation](#) provided participants with a comprehensive understanding of CDSS architecture, the principles of effective dashboard design, and strategies for user experience (UX) evaluation.

Introduction to Clinical Decision Support Systems (CDSS)

CDSS were defined as systems designed to provide clinicians, staff, and patients with intelligently filtered, person-specific information at the right time, enhancing the quality of care. Melissa began by engaging the audience in a discussion about their familiarity with CDSS and their experiences using such systems. This interactive start set the stage for exploring the purpose and architecture of CDSS.

Purpose and core components

The purpose of a CDSS was presented as ensuring the delivery of the **right information** to the **right person**, in the **right format**, through the **right channel**, and at the **right time**. Each element was emphasized as critical to the system's effectiveness, particularly in clinical environments where decisions often have life-critical consequences.

CDSS architecture

The architecture of a CDSS was broken down into several layers:

1. **Knowledge base:** This layer includes programmed rules or machine learning algorithms to support decision-making.
2. **Data management layer:** This layer processes clinical and patient data, typically sourced from electronic health records (EHRs).
3. **Decision layer (Inference Engine):** This layer applies programmed rules or AI models to the clinical data to generate recommendations or actions.
4. **Communication layer (User Interface):** The output from the system is presented to the end-user, such as a clinician, through dashboards, applications, or EHR interfaces.

CDSS architecture

Clinical Decision Support Systems - Enhancing safety and efficacy through design and implementation

Introduction to Clinical Decision Support Systems (CDSS)

Melissa emphasized the distinction between knowledge-based systems, which rely on pre-defined rules, and non-knowledge-based systems, which leverage machine learning models to adapt to new data. Examples of practical applications highlighted how these components interact to provide actionable insights to healthcare providers.

The role of UX/UI in CDSS design

A significant portion of the session was dedicated to the importance of **user experience (UX)** and **user interface (UI)** in the effectiveness of CDSS. Participants were encouraged to consider how design choices impact the usability and safety of these systems.

- **Challenges in dashboard design:** Using examples, Melissa illustrated how cluttered dashboards with excessive information or poor visual hierarchies could overwhelm users, reducing efficiency and increasing the likelihood of errors.
- **Principles of effective dashboards:** The session outlined best practices such as:
 - the *five-second rule* - key information should be immediately visible
 - the *inverted pyramid structure* - most critical information at the top
 - the principle of *minimalism* - removing unnecessary elements

How does UX/UI design affect efficacy?

Clinical Decision Support Systems - Enhancing safety and efficacy through design and implementation

Case study - CDSS for sepsis patients

A real-world example was presented to illustrate the functionality of a well-designed CDSS. The case study focused on a system designed for patients with possible sepsis, demonstrating features such as:

- **Relevant historical data:** Displaying patient vitals and previous health trajectories.
- **State diagrams:** Depicting state transitions and probabilities based on current patient data.
- **Optimal actions:** Suggesting the best and second-best actions based on real-time inputs.
- **Visualization of drug history:** Tracking significant events and allowing for manual recalculations when reward values were adjusted.

This example highlighted how a thoughtfully designed CDSS could not only predict patient outcomes like mortality or length of stay but also empower clinicians to make data-driven decisions.

CDSS for patients with possible sepsis

Plenary session - Data Quality concepts

Introduction to Data Quality

The plenary session, presented by Jens Declerck, PhD student at UGent and Data Quality Manager at i~HD, explored essential data quality concepts and their significance in healthcare. Drawing on real-world examples and innovative European projects, Jens emphasized how improving data quality is integral to enhancing clinical decision-making and fostering health innovation. The session was supported by a detailed [slide deck](#), which can be consulted for further reference.

Defining Data Quality

Jens opened with a fundamental definition: “**Data quality is the degree to which data dimensions meet requirements.**” He emphasized the *fit-for-purpose principle*, explaining that data quality requirements are context-dependent and must evolve with changing use cases and objectives. For example, data needed for clinical decision-making will have different quality expectations than data intended for secondary research or policymaking.

Jens underscored that data quality is not a static concept. Instead, it is a dynamic process that requires continuous assessment and improvement to meet diverse and evolving needs. This concept set the stage for a deeper dive into how data quality dimensions are defined and applied.

The importance of Data Quality dimensions

Jens explored how data quality dimensions are organized into frameworks to systematically evaluate datasets. Common dimensions include:

- **Accuracy:** How closely data aligns with true values.
- **Completeness:** Ensuring all necessary data elements are present.
- **Timeliness:** Whether data is available when needed.
- **Reliability:** The consistency of data across different contexts and use cases.

He emphasized that these dimensions strongly depend on the *requirements of the end-user*:

- For a **medical doctor**, *completeness* may mean having **all relevant data about a specific patient** in their electronic health record.
- For a **researcher** conducting secondary analysis, *completeness* often refers to whether the dataset includes sufficient information about an entire **population subset**.

This variability underscores how user-needs shape the definitions of data quality dimensions, making it challenging to create agnostic frameworks that can be universally applied or externally validated. Jens explained that a practical framework must consider the entire data lifecycle, ensuring it supports each stage of the journey without compromising usability.

Jens offered a practical perspective on data provisioning, which he defined as “how to hand the data over to the next person in the life cycle.” This transfer must balance improving data quality (the vertical axis) with seamless workflows (the horizontal axis), aligning with the DataKlap methodology introduced earlier by Melissa Wittens.

Plenary session - Data Quality concepts

The QUANTUM project

Jens provided insights into the [QUANTUM project](#), an EU-funded initiative aimed at developing a **data quality and utility label** for the European Health Data Space (EHDS). The project's goal is to create a standardized labeling system that guarantees the quality and utility of datasets for scientific research and healthcare innovation. This label will enable researchers, policymakers, and healthcare professionals to identify high-quality datasets for secondary use, such as in decision-making and policy development.

Key highlights of the QUANTUM project:

- **Compliance with EHDS Regulations:** QUANTUM addresses Article 56 of the EHDS regulation proposal, mandating the labeling of health datasets.
- **Capacity Building:** The project includes a learning program and fosters a community of practice to improve data management across Europe.
- **Piloting the Label System:** QUANTUM involves designing, testing, and implementing a labeling system in collaboration with data holders across 15 countries.

The IDERHA project - Linking data for better patient outcomes

Jens also introduced an important outcome of [IDERHA](#), a pioneering project under the European Beating Cancer Plan. This initiative leverages artificial intelligence and machine learning to integrate and analyze diverse health datasets, improving early lung cancer detection and quality of life for patients. i~HD, where Jens is a key contributor, leads the ethical, legal, and regulatory compliance efforts for this AI-driven platform.

The **SOP for Health Data Quality Assurance** presented during the session originated from IDERHA. It serves as a systematic framework for assessing and maintaining high data quality standards at various stages of the data lifecycle. This methodology is particularly relevant for integrating datasets from multiple sources and ensuring that quality dimensions like completeness, accuracy, and timeliness align with intended use cases.

Plenary session - Data Quality concepts

Data Quality challenges

Common Data Quality errors and challenges

Jens elaborated on frequent issues that compromise data quality:

- **Data entry errors:** Mistakes during manual input.
- **System design/user interface flaws:** Poorly designed interfaces leading to misinterpretation.
- **Data silos:** Fragmentation across systems, reducing consistency.
- **Quality loss during mapping:** Errors introduced when converting datasets to e.g. a standard like OMOP CDM.
- **Governance gaps:** Insufficient leadership and accountability for data quality.
- **Cultural barriers:** Lack of a data quality culture and dedicated stakeholders.
- **Awareness and training deficits:** Limited knowledge and skills in data quality management.

These challenges highlight the importance of adopting tailored strategies for data quality improvement.

Data Quality is about the user

Using a relatable analogy, Jens shared how teaching his son to organize Lego bricks by color helped prevent losses and enabled smoother construction. This analogy illustrated the value of structuring and organizing data to make it accessible and usable. He reiterated that **data quality is about the user**, emphasizing that well-organized, reliable data directly impacts its utility in clinical and research settings.

The enigma of data (quality): an analogy of Big Data with Lego pieces

Plenary session - Data Quality concepts

Data Quality challenges

Strategies for improvement

Jens presented a comprehensive framework for managing data quality:

1. **Purpose and scope definition:** Clear objectives ensure alignment with user needs.
2. **Data Quality planning:** Identifying key quality dimensions relevant to specific datasets.
3. **Data acquisition and preparation:** Robust processes for collecting and transforming data.
4. **Data provisioning:** Structured annotation, labeling, and encoding to maintain integrity

i-HD's Data Quality Management framework

Key takeaways

The session concluded with actionable insights:

1. **Adopt standards:** Utilize tools like the SOP to systematically assess and improve data quality.
2. **Leverage EU projects:** Engage with initiatives like QUANTUM and IDERHA to align with best practices and EHDS regulations.
3. **Invest in training:** Foster awareness and build capacity among healthcare professionals and data managers.
4. **Focus on users:** Design systems and processes with usability and accessibility as priorities.

Jens emphasized that improving data quality is a shared responsibility, requiring collaboration, governance, and a user-centered approach. By addressing challenges and leveraging innovative methodologies, healthcare organizations can unlock the full potential of their data.

Breakout session - Roles & responsibilities in Data Quality

General introduction - How to put Data Quality on the agenda (or not)?

This session, led and designed by Noëlla Pierlet, Head of the Data Science Unit at [ZOL](#) and PhD student in the [Biomedical Data Sciences research group at UHasselt](#), provided participants with a hands-on opportunity to explore roles and responsibilities in data quality. Noëlla's expertise in integrating clinical and data-driven approaches ensured the session was both practical and engaging.

The session began with an [insightful introduction](#) by Noëlla, reflecting on her own experiences in a hospital setting. She framed the discussion with four key Points of View (POVs) that highlighted the challenges and opportunities of elevating data quality within healthcare organizations:

General introduction: How to put Data Quality on the agenda (or not)?

1. POV 1: Real-World Data is indispensable, but reactive behavior persists

- While the importance of real-world data (RWD) is no longer questioned at the management level, Noëlla shared that hospitals often operate reactively. Leaders may rush to demand immediate insights during crises, but this urgency often contrasts with a lack of proactive investment in building sustainable data quality practices.

2. POV 2: Growing attention, limited action

- Although awareness of data quality is increasing, Noëlla observed that it often remains superficial. Endless meetings and debates about data meaning and interpretation lead to inaction, reflecting a gap in true understanding.

3. POV 3: Data Quality doesn't need to be perfect

- She advocated for a pragmatic approach, emphasizing that transparency about data limitations is more critical than striving for unattainable perfection. The usability of data should align with its intended purpose, which she illustrated using a "Dataedo" cartoon highlighting the risks of overconfidence in healthcare data.

4. POV 4: Challenges in prioritizing data quality

- Noëlla highlighted several hurdles to improving data quality:
 - Lack of organizational support and expertise.
 - The complexity of implementing and maintaining quality standards.
 - The significant effort required to launch data quality initiatives.

She emphasized the importance of engaging management and care providers, each of whom play distinct yet interconnected roles in data quality improvement.

Breakout session - Roles & responsibilities in Data Quality

General introduction - How to put Data Quality on the agenda (or not)?

The ROI for healthcare providers

One of Noëlla’s key messages was that healthcare providers need to see direct benefits from data quality initiatives. While academic research, government submissions, and collaborations with industry are valuable, they rarely resonate with frontline healthcare professionals. Instead, the ROI for care providers lies in:

- Increased efficiency through automation.
- Streamlined multidisciplinary workflows.
- Simplified, minimal data entry processes.
- Robust data linkages enabling easier access and analysis.
- Transparent trajectory monitoring to identify and resolve bottlenecks.

She stressed that addressing these operational needs supports buy-in among healthcare providers, making them active participants in the data quality process. For example, trajectory analysis—similar to the morning’s use case presented by Nicky Van der Vekens—offers a tangible starting point to identify and co-create solutions with care providers, ultimately improving outcomes for everyone involved.

The ROI for healthcare providers

Breakout session - Roles & responsibilities in Data Quality

Use Case - Telemonitoring for chronic heart failure

Following the introduction, participants were tasked with applying these concepts to a real-world use case based on the legal requirements of [Article 56§1 of the Belgian Health Insurance Act](#), which formalizes telemonitoring pathways. This legislation defines the obligations of healthcare institutions, telemonitoring teams, and patients. Participants were tasked with operationalizing these requirements through a detailed data quality lens, with an emphasis on creating compliant, efficient workflows.

Breakout group insights

A highlight of the session was the breakout group discussions. One group presented the following interpretation:

1. Data to be provided to the government

- The required data includes all information necessary for the RIZIV's Service for Medical Care to assess compliance with therapeutic and financial plans. This data also supports overall management of the telemonitoring program.

2. Defining phase completion

- A phase is deemed complete when its tasks and objectives are fully achieved, criteria are met, and necessary validations are obtained.

3. Stakeholders

- **RIZIV:** Oversees compliance and financial aspects.
- **Hospitals and Medical Directors:** Supervise telemonitoring teams.
- **Telemonitoring teams:** Include cardiology specialists and heart failure nurses managing data and care.
- **Primary Care Providers:** Maintain patient medical records.
- **Patients:** Contribute consistent data and adhere to care plans.
- **Home nurses:** Provide additional support if applicable.

4. Triggers for transition between phases

- **Inclusion criteria:** Diagnosis of heart failure and recent hospitalization for acute decompensation.
- **Monitoring initiation:** Telemonitoring starts during hospitalization or within two weeks post-discharge.
- **Data monitoring and alarms:** Regular submission of health data triggers clinical actions.
- **Therapeutic adjustments:** Initiated based on validated alarms and assessments.
- **Stop criteria:** Monitoring ceases if criteria are unmet, or by patient or medical decision.

Collaborative outputs - Designing an ideal data flow

The groups co-created an ideal data flow compliant with legal and clinical standards. Key elements included:

- Integration of data sources to eliminate silos and enhance interoperability.
- Establishing checkpoints for data validation at critical phases of the workflow.
- Secure reporting to the government, ensuring transparency and compliance.
- Real-time dashboards for monitoring alarms and guiding therapeutic responses.

Breakout session - Roles & responsibilities in Data Quality

Use Case - Telemonitoring for chronic heart failure

Conclusion: Strengthening roles and responsibilities

Noëlla closed the session with a reflection on the broader implications of data quality:

- Engaging stakeholders early and co-creating solutions are essential for sustained improvement.
- Transparent processes and trajectory analysis provide tangible benefits, promoting trust and collaboration across teams.
- A dedicated data team is crucial to support care providers and ensure practical implementation.

This session underscored that data quality improvement is not just a technical task—it is an organizational commitment that requires alignment, education, and continuous effort.

References & resources

- Workshop slide decks
 - [Use-Case presentation Nicky](#)
 - [CDSS Melissa](#)
 - [Plenary session Jens](#)
 - [Breakout session Noëlla](#)
- Other interesting reads
 - [White paper - Health Data Quality: A Dynamic Complexity](#)
 - [TEHDAS Quality Framework](#)

Final thoughts and next steps

The workshop underscored that **data quality improvement is a shared responsibility** requiring alignment across stakeholders, tailored strategies, and continuous education. The practical insights and collaborative spirit of this event set a strong foundation for future initiatives.

To maintain the momentum generated by this workshop, OHDSI Belgium has committed to taking an active role in furthering awareness and driving collaborative action on data quality improvement. As a next step, OHDSI Belgium will be a strategic partner at the [upcoming i~HD Health Data Summit, taking place on 19-20 March 2025 in The Egg, Brussels](#). This summit will provide a critical platform to unite thought leaders, healthcare professionals, policymakers, and technology providers to advance the conversation on health data quality under the theme: **“High-quality data to deliver tomorrow’s healthcare.”**

OHDSI Belgium’s participation will include:

1. **Opening plenary leadership:** Liesbet Peeters, co-chair of OHDSI Belgium, will chair the opening plenary session, setting the stage for impactful discussions on the future of health data quality.
2. **Expert contributions:** Noëlla Pierlet (ZOL) and Bart Vannieuwenhuysse (Core Group member, OHDSI Belgium) will share their expertise as keynote speakers.
3. **Panel discussions:** Nicky Van der Vekens and Annelies Verbiest will engage in panel discussions to provide actionable insights from their work on improving health data pipelines.
4. **Educational tutorial:** OHDSI Belgium will host a tutorial aimed at introducing OHDSI to newcomers. The session will emphasize how being part of this community and using its tools for harmonized analyses can benefit the setup of health data sharing initiatives or large-scale network studies.

Call to Action

The journey toward high-quality health data requires continuous collaboration, innovation, and shared accountability. All stakeholders—healthcare professionals, researchers, policymakers, and technologists—are encouraged to:

- **Participate in the i~HD Health Data Summit 2025:** Engage in thought-provoking discussions, learn from leading experts, and gain actionable strategies for data quality improvement.
- **Advocate for Data Quality as a priority:** Raise awareness within your organization about the strategic importance of high-quality health data, emphasizing its impact on patient care, research, and policy.
- **Leverage tools and resources:** Explore the tools and frameworks developed by OHDSI and other initiatives to implement scalable and sustainable data quality practices.
- **Collaborate across sectors:** Promote partnerships that bridge technical, clinical, and policy domains to address complex challenges in data management.

By committing to these actions, we can collectively ensure that health data serves as a reliable foundation for advancements in patient care, clinical research, and healthcare policy, unlocking its full potential for a healthier future.

Annex - About the organizers

OHDSI Belgium

The Belgian OHDSI Node was born spontaneously from the Belgian EHDEN community. After several members expressed their interest to form a Node, we organized a brief poll among Belgian EHDEN data partners, certified SMEs and their networks. This generated a lot of enthusiastic responses, not only from the current community, but also from aspiring data partners and several other stakeholders. In a short time, the Node had been established (June 2023).

The Node members realize that, in order to leverage health data to improve citizen health, we need an enabling foundation that is trustworthy for citizens and offers FAIR data with a clear governance model. Therefore, besides promoting Belgian participation in OHDSI network studies, the Node aims to contribute to a harmonized Belgian health data ecosystem that is aligned with the European OHDSI chapter and the European Health Data Space and specific national legislations. It takes a hands-on approach, focused on getting things done following the OHDSI open-source and open-science principles.

More information can be found on [OHDSI Belgium's website](#) or [LinkedIn](#) page.

VZW Maria Middelaes - Nicky Van der Vekens

Nicky Van Der Vekens is a Staff member CEO - digital hospital coordinator at VZW Maria Middelaes in Ghent, Belgium. She is also a Core Group member of OHDSI Belgium. In both roles, Nicky strives to bridge the gap between digital data-driven innovations and healthcare providers, aiming to support efficient operations and improve patient outcomes. Her expertise encompasses clinical data management, research coordination, and policy-making in the healthcare sector. More information can be found on the [VZW Maria Middelaes](#) website or [Nicky's LinkedIn](#) page.

imec-SMIT-VUB - Melissa Wittens

Mandy 'Melissa' Jane is a senior researcher at [imec-SMIT-VUB](#), specializing in enhancing trustworthiness and transparency in the secondary use of data within health data spaces. Her work focuses on implementing measures that promote data quality, interoperability, and accessibility to facilitate secure data sharing.

Melissa investigates key challenges in data governance within healthcare settings and defines essential components of trustworthy clinical decision support systems (CDSS). She also explores how Human in The Loop (HITL) approaches can improve the interpretability and trustworthiness of AI. More information can be found on [Melissa's LinkedIn](#) page.

Annex - About the organizers

European Institute for Innovation through Health Data (i~HD) - Jens Declerck

Jens Declerck is the Data Quality Manager at the European Institute for Innovation through Health Data ([i~HD](#)). In this role, he is responsible for coordinating data quality projects, which include study design, preparation, data quality assessment, improvement strategies, and reporting. His work focuses on enhancing the quality and trustworthiness of health data to maximize its potential in healthcare settings.

In addition to his role at i~HD, Jens is also involved in academic research at UGent, focusing on areas such as orthopaedics, human movement and sports sciences, and rehabilitation sciences. More information about Jens Declerck can be found on his [LinkedIn](#) profile.

The banner for the Health Data 25 Summit features the i~HD logo on the left, which includes the text 'The European Institute for Innovation through Health Data'. Next to it is a QR code and the text 'REGISTER NOW' with the URL 'i-hd.eu/hds2025'. The main title 'HEALTH DATA 25 SUMMIT' is in large, bold letters, with '25' in pink and 'SUMMIT' in blue. Below the title is the tagline 'High-quality data delivering tomorrow's healthcare'. A circular badge on the left side of the banner says 'THE EGG BRUSSELS 19-20 MARCH 2025'. At the bottom right, it says 'Advancing healthcare, fostering innovation and accelerating research through strategic data quality management'.

Ziekenhuis Oost-Limburg (ZOL) - Noëlla Pierlet

Noëlla Pierlet is Head of Data Science at Ziekenhuis Oost-Limburg ([ZOL](#)) and a PhD candidate in the research group of [Biomedical Data Sciences at Hasselt University](#). Her work focuses on data quality and its role in improving quality of care. With a strong technical background, Noëlla excels in process and workflow analysis, driving improvements in planning, organization, and project management.

Combining a passion for learning with a results-driven mindset, she is dedicated to delivering high-quality outcomes within set deadlines. Her expertise lies in bridging data science and healthcare operations, fostering solutions that enhance both patient care and organizational efficiency. More information can be found on [Noëlla's LinkedIn](#) page.

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